

FAIRmat Newsletter

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Editorial

Dear FAIRmat family, welcome to the eighth FAIRmat Newsletter!

The end of the year has always meant a moment of reflection: looking back on what has been achieved, or maybe missed, and setting the frame for what is going to be aimed at. Without a doubt, 2025 has been an extremely eventful year for FAIRmat.

On the one hand, there were the interim-report symposium, the submission of the renewal proposal for the second funding phase, and, quite recently at the beginning of December, the review meeting. The latter went very well, and although you never know on the science-political stage, we are all fully convinced that FAIRmat will get the formal “go” to continue its success story. Many thanks to our five fabulous “defenders”: Eva, Heiko, Silvana, Pepe, and Claudia!

On the other hand, as you can again read in this newsletter, FAIRmat and its software basis, NOMAD, are also technically very successful: more partners, more users, more functionality, more data, and more research enabled by these. The FAIRmat infrastructure is the backbone of this development and definitely a unique selling point of FAIRmat within the NFDI.

That is a wonderful starting point for the new year, which will bring the transition to FAIRmat’s new funding phase. Thanks to all who contributed, and all the best for 2026!

Hans-Joachim Bungartz

Co-spokesperson and leader of Area D: Infrastructure

FAIRmat news

FAIRmat submits renewal proposal to the DFG

On August 6, 2025, FAIRmat submitted its [renewal proposal to the German Research Foundation \(DFG\)](#). This marks an important step toward continuing the development of a comprehensive FAIR data infrastructure for condensed-matter physics and the chemical physics of solids. In the renewal application, FAIRmat introduces two new strategic areas: *Data Modeling and Interoperability*, and *Data-Driven Science*, reflecting the central role of structured, interoperable, and AI-ready research data in materials science. The proposal also highlights the consortium’s broadening scientific base, with principal investigators now representing institutions across 11 German states, as well as strengthened collaborations with international partners, industry, and network projects.

On-site LLM Hackathon for Applications in Materials and Chemistry in Berlin

FAIRmat hosted the on-site part of [the 3rd LLM Hackathon for Applications in Materials Science and Chemistry](#) on September 11–12, 2025, at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. Participants from across Germany explored how large language models can accelerate discovery in materials science and chemistry. The FAIRmat teams [Parse Patrol](#), [Ragalicious](#), and [MatterMinds](#) took part in the event, with Parse Patrol and Ragalicious receiving [Visionary Awards](#) and presenting in a showcase session. The Berlin site also gained international visibility when *Science* featured the event in an article by Zack Savitsky titled [Researchers customize AI tools at global ‘hackathon’](#).

Glaide Data: commercial RDM services supporting the FAIRmat community

[Glaide Data GmbH](#), a spin-off from the FAIRmat project, was recently founded to help scale and operationalize advanced research data management (RDM) solutions. Established by Sebastian Brückner and co-led by Joseph Rudzinski, the company is already supporting several institutions with NOMAD Oasis deployments.

As FAIRmat's official partner, Glaide Data complements the consortium's efforts with commercial services that include installing and hosting NOMAD Oasis, developing custom plugins and schemas, integrating laboratory instruments and automated data pipelines, maintaining NOMAD infrastructures, and providing RDM strategy consulting and hands-on training.

With extensive experience across the NOMAD ecosystem, Glaide Data makes FAIR data practices accessible in any research environment. This reduces the technical burden of RDM for scientists and accelerates the adoption of AI-ready workflows.

Project milestones

Scaling with the community

FAIRmat continues to scale its research data infrastructure by enabling institutes and research groups to participate directly in the NOMAD ecosystem. With *more than 80 registered NOMAD Oases* deployed across universities, research institutes, and laboratories, groups of all sizes can operate local installations, manage their data according to the FAIR principles, and stay connected to the broader infrastructure when needed.

The NOMAD plugin ecosystem has become a central driver of this growth. With *161 NOMAD plugins developed by more than 60 contributors and more than 2,320 merge requests*, the community actively extends NOMAD with support for new data types, methods, and workflows. This bottom-up development model ensures that the platform evolves in step with the needs of its users. Through these contributions, FAIRmat continues to democratize research data management and strengthen a distributed, community-driven infrastructure for the physical sciences.

Schematics of a federated network of NOMAD Oasis installations, demonstrating interoperability between institutional repositories and the central NOMAD service, aggregating multi-institutional datasets.

FAIRmat drives new NeXus standards for materials science

In close collaboration with the NeXus International Advisory Committee (NIAC), FAIRmat experts have expanded the NeXus data format into a versatile standard for a wide range of materials-science experiments.

A key result is the development of new application definitions, which specify what information must be recorded for a given experiment and how it should be structured. They ensure that data produced across different laboratories follow a consistent format, enabling interoperability, reproducibility, and automated processing which is essential for FAIR and AI-ready workflows.

The new definitions cover major techniques: atom probe microscopy ([NXapm](#)), electron microscopy ([NXem](#)), optical spectroscopy ([NXoptical_spectroscopy](#), [NXellipsometry](#), and [NXraman](#)), and photoemission and core-level spectroscopy ([NXmpes](#), [NXmpes_arpes](#), and [NXxps](#)).

All new definitions are fully integrated into NOMAD, allowing researchers to upload, explore, and share NeXus-formatted data with preserved semantics through NOMAD's schema-based Metainfo system.

The FAIRmat infrastructure

Lauri Himanen

Technical coordinator of
Area D: Infrastructure

During the second half of 2025, we focused on delivering several major enhancements to the NOMAD software. This work culminated in the release of NOMAD version 1.4.0 and the alpha launch of our new graphical user interface. Below are some of the key highlights.

New processing engine

We have completely refactored NOMAD's data processing engine – the core component responsible for handling all uploaded data. As a foundational part of our technology stack, this upgrade brings significant improvements:

- Better control: users can now stop and restart the upload processing without administrator support.
- Improved fault tolerance: the new pipelines are far more resilient to system failures such as machine restarts. A built-in heartbeat mechanism detects terminated or stuck processes.
- Better observability: administrators now have access to a detailed processing dashboard, enabling easier debugging and selective restarts of pipeline stages.
- Scalability: large NOMAD deployments can now scale processing replicas directly via Kubernetes, allowing the system to adapt to demand.

These improvements make the processing pipeline more robust, transparent, and responsive, ultimately providing a smoother experience for both users and administrators.

NOMAD Actions

NOMAD Actions introduce a powerful and flexible way to automate tasks across the platform. Defined in Python and integrated via plugins, they can be triggered either through the user interface or via an API call. They support a wide range of use cases, including automated upload workflows such as creating batches of entries from a template, fetching data to pre-fill ELNs, and launching machine-learning training jobs that work directly on NOMAD-stored data. Actions can also run ML models to perform analysis tasks or generate new data.

NOMAD Actions are designed to scale seamlessly from quick operations that run in under a second to long-running jobs that take days on specialized GPU-enabled workers with custom Docker images. This flexibility ensures that NOMAD can support modern ML pipelines end-to-end.

Although this feature is still in an early integration phase, some early adopters are already experimenting with automated phase identification from XRD patterns using probabilistic deep-learning models implemented as NOMAD Actions. These developments pave the way toward making NOMAD the de-facto platform for data-driven scientific workflows.

NOMAD GUI

We have also been working on a completely redesigned user interface for NOMAD, and we are excited to announce that the *alpha version* is now available for internal testing and early feedback. The new GUI has been designed to significantly improve the overall user experience. It features a mobile-friendly design that has been developed specifically for use on mobile devices and tablets, making it ideal for researchers who need to edit ELNs directly in the lab. We are also building support for more flexible, schema-aware layouts to help schema developers craft more informative entry overviews. The new GUI has shifted from a horizontal to a more intuitive vertical navigation structure, giving users clearer context and orientation within the platform.

Performance when working with large amounts of data has also been greatly enhanced, enabling users to browse and edit large entries more quickly and efficiently. Finally, uploads will be called “projects”, with the previous “dataset” concept integrated under this term to simplify DOI creation and data migration.

We are working toward a beta release, at which point we will invite members of the NOMAD community to provide feedback and ensure the interface reflects the needs of our diverse user base.

Meet our users

Sathya Sai Seetharaman

Senior computational scientist
Science and Technology Facilities
Council, UK

What is the research focus in your group?

Our research at the Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) focuses on analyzing crystal structures to gain atomic-level insight into structure, disorder, and dynamics in the solid state. We do so by combining experimental Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) data with *ab initio* calculations from Density Functional Theory (DFT) codes.

Since most researchers already use spreadsheets to plan experiments, we closely collaborated with them to develop a spreadsheet template that feeds directly into NOMAD. It is compatible with our metadata parsers and dramatically lowered the entry barrier. Suddenly, scientists could upload their data independently, and they did.

What challenges do scientists face when applying the FAIR principles to their research data?

Solid-state NMR computational outputs are heterogeneous across DFT codes and often lack the contextual metadata needed for downstream scientific use. As the volume of NMR data grows, the challenge is no longer just producing results, but ensuring that they remain consistent across our database and properly embedded in a FAIR ecosystem.

A central challenge is that NMR calculations typically emerge from diverse electronic-structure codes, each representing the same quantities in different ways. CCP-NC's strategy to address this inconsistency is to use our [magres format](#) as the unifying standard and build the community infrastructure around it. For legacy datasets, the original simulation files may no longer exist, making provenance reconstruction particularly challenging. These gaps make it difficult to apply the FAIR principles consistently and greatly limit the reusability of published NMR data.

What is the strategy for RDM in your group and how is FAIRmat helping in implementing it?

Over the past year, we have been developing our NOMAD Oasis instance to host, annotate, and serve the CCP-NC magres database, integrating both existing NMR schema and new extensions that support additional quantities. We have also introduced community-specific custom metadata such as free-text structural notes, chemical names, ORCID-linked contributor information to name a few. The goal is to make NMR data searchable by property, chemical environment, tensor features, or provenance attributes, allowing researchers to focus on analysis rather than manual data cleaning.

FAIRmat has significantly supported our efforts to implement FAIR data practices. The NOMAD platform provides the infrastructure, schema tooling, and customizable interface that enable a domain-specific community, such as CCP-NC, to establish a fully FAIR database without having to build every layer themselves. Through consultations, workshops, and schema-design discussions with FAIRmat experts, we have been able to align our work with broader materials-science data standards while retaining the specificity needed by the NMR community.

This collaboration is helping us bring together diverse datasets into an interoperable, community-governed resource that both improves current research and unlocks future data-driven advance towards machine-learning applications in NMR crystallography.

Meet our experts

Sarthak Kapoor

Domain expert in Area A: Synthesis

What motivated you to join FAIRmat?

Although material scientists collect highly valuable data throughout their research, only a small fraction of such data becomes accessible via publications. The challenge is rarely the lack of willingness to share data, rather, it is the lack of user-friendly and low-threshold platforms that prevents researchers from doing so. FAIRmat is addressing this gap by working closely with scientists

on building an exceptional ecosystem that promotes data structuring and sharing. I connect deeply with its overarching goals of making scientific data FAIR and building strong communities alongside. Joining it was one of the easiest decisions I have ever made.

What is your role at FAIRmat?

I develop data models and analysis tools for the material synthesis community. This includes contributing to NOMAD plugins for material characterization and processing methods. Currently, I am working extensively to build inherent support in NOMAD for scientific machine-learning and data analysis. For this, I collaborate closely with our data infrastructure team to develop new features for the platform. Besides platform development, my routine work also includes providing support to our research lab partners for setting up and maintaining their custom instances of NOMAD Oases. I thoroughly enjoy the interdisciplinary nature of my work.

What is your favorite thing about working at FAIRmat?

The best part of my job is working with our users, who are making tremendous contributions to our understanding of materials and pushing forward the possibilities. We work closely to understand their data management needs and help them in meeting these requirements. To be a small part of their journey is truly an honor for me. In the process, we also learn a lot about how to improve our platform. This back-and-forth communication between users and developers is simply beautiful and inspiring.

Opinion article

Christof Wöll

Co-spokesperson and leader of Area E: Use Cases

The 2025 Nobel Prize in Chemistry was awarded to Susumu Kitagawa, Richard Robson, and Omar M. Yaghi for developing a new class of materials, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) – porous, crystalline compounds with exceptionally large internal surface areas. Their pioneering work established a platform for precise molecular design relevant to gas storage, catalysis, water harvesting, and environmental remediation [1].

An important characteristic of this new class of molecular solids, formed by linking organic ligands with metal or metal-oxo nodes (often referred to as crystalline coordination networks, CCNs), is the immense size of the accessible chemical space. More than 100 000 MOFs have been synthesized and structurally characterized by X-ray diffraction, while computational screenings exceed 2 million predicted structures. Considering the virtually unlimited diversity of organic molecules, there is no inherent upper limit to the number of possible MOFs.

While gas storage and separation motivated the Nobel recognition, far more advanced applications are now in focus. The ability to arrange chromophores – organic units with tailored optical and electronic properties – within well-defined crystalline lattices and with bespoke band structures enables chemical sensors, organic solar cells, light-emitting devices, organic electronics, and even quantum materials with Dirac-cone electronic structures. MOFs also offer unique opportunities for magnetic materials, as their modular architectures allow incorporation of paramagnetic ions, spin-bearing linkers, and exchange-coupled clusters, enabling tunable low-dimensional magnetism and field- or light-switchable magnetic phases.

A particularly attractive feature is the ability to load functional guests into the pores. Beyond small molecules, MOFs can host switchable species (photochromic, redox-active, or acid-base responsive) whose states can be altered by light, pH changes, or applied voltage. Switching can be achieved either by incorporating switchable linkers directly into the MOF backbone or by loading switchable molecules into the pores, thus enabling multiple pathways toward responsive, reconfigurable materials. The defined pore environment also allows stabilization of small metal clusters, semiconductor nanoclusters, and even single atoms, unlocking catalytic, optical, or magnetic functionalities that are inaccessible in bulk materials.

MOFs are also central to the digitalization of materials science. Their crystallinity enables accurate first-principles predictions of physical properties, while machine-learning methods now support automated inference of synthetic routes from large collections of reported procedures. Often the synthesis of MOFs and MOF thin films with desired electronic band structures poses a formidable

problem. In this context, self-driving labs (SDLs) can be used to optimize experimental parameters efficiently [2].

Because MOFs combine structural regularity, tunability, and chemical richness, MOFs are ideally suited for inclusion in materials databases such as NOMAD, where structural data, computed properties, and synthesis information can be integrated for data-driven discovery. With more than [17,000 MOF entries available in NOMAD](#), the data are stored not only in standard crystallographic formats (such as CIF or POSCAR) but also enriched with a dedicated metadata schema capturing structural information. This schema records intrinsic material characteristics, including topology, linker identities, metal nodes, pore metrics, and accessible surface area. Because these descriptors are linked to workflow provenance, each entry is traceable and reproducible. This integrated representation of structure, calculations, and topology allows researchers to explore, compare, and analyze MOFs in a FAIR manner. This approach supports data-driven discovery and reproducible MOF research.

References:

- [1] [Freund et al., Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 60, 23946, \(2021\)](#).
- [2] [Scheiger et al., Mater. Horiz. 12, 6189, \(2025\)](#).

Collaboration with other NFDI consortia

Over the past few months, FAIRmat has further strengthened its collaboration with fellow NFDI consortia. [The Conference on Research Data Infrastructure \(CoRDI\) 2025](#) brought the entire NFDI community together, sparking valuable discussions and fresh ideas. At the [Microscopy Conference \(MC2025\)](#), we participated with a joint booth alongside the NFDI consortia MatWerk and NFDI4BIOIMAGE, and co-organized a pre-conference workshop on [Research Data Management \(RDM\) in Microscopy](#). Building on this, we continued our joint-booth approach at [the 2nd DPG Fall Meeting](#) in Göttingen (September 8–12), collaborating with DAPHNE4NFDI, PUNCH4NFDI, and NFDI4Cat to engage the scientific community collectively. Together with NFDI4Chem, we participated in and co-organized a dedicated RDM workshop for the DFG Research Unit [Energy Landscapes and Structure in Ion Conducting Solids \(ELSICS\)](#). The workshop offered the FAIRmat team an excellent opportunity to better understand the RDM needs and practices of research units like ELSICS, thereby

strengthening the dialogue between infrastructure developers and the scientific community.

Outreach and training

The second half of 2025 kept us busy with community engagement through a number of conferences, workshops, and meetings. Our efforts culminated in [the 7th FAIRmat Users Meeting](#) (November 20), which drew more than 100 NOMAD users and developers to exchange best practices, explore new developments, and strengthen community ties.

Our training activities were spread across Europe. On October 20–24, Joseph Rudzinski co-organized and represented FAIRmat at the [MADICES 2025 workshop](#) in Villigen, Switzerland, giving an overview of interoperability features within the NOMAD platform. Our team also took part in the [OPTIMADE workshop](#) (September 15–19) in Vilnius, Lithuania, where participants worked on extending interoperability across materials databases.

FAIRmat continued to present NOMAD at major national and international conferences. At the [Psi-k Conference](#) in Switzerland (August 25–28), which brings together the computational condensed-matter physics community, FAIRmat had an information booth, co-organized several symposia, and contributed talks. This enabled direct interaction with researchers in electronic-structure theory and data-driven materials science. At the [International Conference on Silicon Carbide and Related Materials \(ICSCRM\)](#) in South Korea (September 14–19), a leading conference in silicon carbide and semiconductor research, FAIRmat had a gold booth in the exhibition area, providing visibility within both the academic and industrial communities.

The full list of our past and upcoming events can be found on the [FAIRmat events](#) page. Thank you for your ongoing interest and engagement – we look forward to many more occasions in 2026!

Upcoming events

Next year, we will keep organizing and participating in various events across Germany and Europe, offering talks, workshops, and opportunities to connect in person:

- [DPG Spring Meeting of the Condensed Matter Section \(SKM\)](#), March 8–13, 2026 – Dresden, Germany
- [Bunsen-Tagung 2026](#), March 30 – April 1, 2026 – Dresden, Germany
- [RDM Spring School](#), April 13–16, 2026 – Erlangen, Germany
- [European Materials Research Society \(E-MRS\) Spring Meeting](#), May 26–28, 2026 – Strasbourg, France

To stay informed and never miss an event, visit our [events page](#), [subscribe](#) to email updates, and follow us on [LinkedIn](#). We are continually adding new opportunities related to NOMAD education and community building.

Recent publications

- J. Schumann, H. Näsström, M. Götze, L. Himanen, A. Moshantaf, M. Scheidgen, J. A. Márquez Prieto, C. Draxl, and A. Trunschke, *Towards a new era for open and FAIR data in catalysis research – A catalysis plugin for NOMAD*, Nat. Catal., in print (2025).
- A. Maqsood, H. Näsström, C. Chen, L. Qitong, J. Luo, R. Chakraborty, V. Blum, E. Unger, C. Draxl, J. A. Márquez, and T. Jesper Jacobsson, *Towards an interoperable perovskite description or how to keep track of 300 perovskite ions*, Nat. Commun. 16, 8725 (2025).
- N. Alampara, M. Schilling-Wilhelmi, M. Ríos-García, I. Mandal, P. Khetarpal, H. S. Grover, N. M. Anoop Krishnan, and K. M. Jablonka, *Probing the limitations of multimodal language models for chemistry and materials research*, Nat. Comput. Sci. 5, 952–961 (2025).

The full list of our publications and invited talks can be found on our [website](#).

The FAIRmat team

Welcome to our new coworkers!

Berfin Güner
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Alice Appel
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Stay in touch

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NOMAD Discord!

Join our NOMAD Discord, where you can connect with fellow researchers, share ideas, and get answers.

NOMAD Oasis

Register your NOMAD Oasis to be informed with software updates and news.

Selected shots from the last few months

Our team at the 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI)

Bringing FAIRmat to the global stage at ICSCRM Busan

Engaging with the community at the 7th Users Meeting in Berlin

RDM Workshop for the DFG Research Unit ELSICS at Marburg University

On-site LLM Hackathon for Applications in Materials and Chemistry in Berlin

Joint NFDI Consortia booth at DPG Fall Meeting in Göttingen